

Counterfactual design

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Abstract: Honesty is a time-honoured principle in professional design, an axiomatic element of conventional design wisdom expressed in catchphrases like ‘form follows function’ and ‘truth to materials.’ However, not all design follows the honesty principle. This paper discusses *counterfactual design*; a class of design that intentionally appears to be something it is not. Counterfactual design bends the truth to varying degrees. This paper distinguishes between counterfactual design in which the truth is edited, on standby, and suspended. It discusses the intentions behind counterfactual design, which range from beautification and amusement, to ersatz and deception. These classes of counterfactual design deal with the improvement of something existing, a quest for otherness, a quest for likeness, and outright cheating respectively. The paper continues by discussing how the truth is bent: by overstatement, by fabrication, and by understatement, sometimes practiced overtly and at other times, covertly. It concludes with the suggestion that, contrary to popular belief, several types of counterfactual design are honourable design practices.

Key words: *counterfactual design, beautification, amusement, ersatz, deception*

1. Introduction

This paper introduces a previously unstudied area of design practise, counterfactual design. To be or not to be, the basic question in philosophy and life obscures by its dichotomous simplicity a third possibility: pretending without being, the territory of counterfactual design. Objects that pretend to be something that they are not emanate from many design disciplines. Counterfactual design seduces the spectator by appearing ‘better’ than it is. Both academic and trade design literature has hitherto ignored this important category of design activity. Counterfactual design bends the truth to varying degrees, depending on the objectives and the intended effect. This paper describes ways to classify counterfactual design according to similarities and differences. After a full discussion of the nature and properties of counterfactual design, this paper makes a case for counterfactual design to be acknowledged as a legitimate and honourable area of design activity in future research into design practise. Much good design is not honest in the strict sense of the word, but nevertheless improves our quality of life.

2. A matter of form

Everyday objects, the things we use to go about in our daily business, are tools; they have practical functions, that is their *raison d’être*. If the objects had no practical function we would, in principle, not need them and they

would not exist. They have a *form* which, according to conventional design wisdom, *follows function* [1] and demonstrates *truth to materials*. The form represents the intended function and respects and reveals the material it is made of.

The aesthetic pleasure and symbolic interest aroused by designed everyday objects vary drastically. For some objects the outside form means as much as, or more than, the technical function. In special cases the form *is* the function. Fashion is a case in point, but form also has paramount importance in more mundane tools and appliances, even if the buyers and users don't recognise it.

As a rule, the form of designed everyday objects says something about their function and their production. But the form often reveals more than merely function and materials. The form can – among other things – also tell who made the object, and hint at who uses it. A Bang & Olufsen sound system makes no secret of its provenance and openly suggests that the owner is well off. A beautiful red lip-gloss sends sweet messages ready for interpretation.

It is a basic assumption that everyday objects speak the truth. In fact, conventional design wisdom holds that the form of manmade objects must be honest, but counterfactual design is not honest in the demanding sense of that word. It does not express the truth. Counterfactual design says something fictitious about its provenance, its function, or its user. Who is responsible for counterfactual design? The designer, of course. But here it must be remembered that design is not an activity that is exclusively practiced by professional designers. We are all designers when we take design decisions, for instance when we decide how we will decorate our home, dress up for the carnival, or dress down for a quiet day at the office.

3. Related research

Product semantics, a relatively new discipline deal with the ways designers invest meaning and users see meaning in products. American designers Klaus Krippendorff and Reinhart Butter introduced the term in 1984. Since then Krippendorff has fathered a substantial part of the literature on product semantics including the seminal work *The Semantic Turn* [2]. Writers about product semantics have primarily been interested in instructional messages and have only dealt superficially – or not at all – with the aesthetic, social, and intentionally misleading messages that constitute counterfactual design. They have apparently had honesty in design as an unwritten assumption.

4. Bending the truth

Counterfactual design bends the truth, but the results of truth bending do not fit into all or nothing categories. Truth bending is a continuum on which this paper proposes three positions. They are in rising order: *truth edited*, *truth on standby*, and *truth suspended*. These three positions are not watertight compartments; the distinctions between them are not sharp.

We are used to truth bending in speech and writing. But the spoken and written language is not alone in dealing sloppily with truth. Objects for everyday use, buildings, and entire environments can also send messages that

more or less innocently manipulate reality. Things talk. The English critic John Ruskin suggested that buildings have two functions: to shelter and to talk [3]. It is the same with all other manmade objects with useful purposes. They talk their silent language to anybody who cares to listen, and the stories are copious. Where the things originate; of what, how, and by whom they are made, what they should be used for, how they should be used, and who uses them. Design is a language.

5. Seduction

The language of design can, like spoken language, be true, almost true, or outright mendacious. It complies fully with Umberto Eco's definition of the subject of semiotics: 'everything that can be used in order to lie' [4]. What things say about identity, provenance, function, operation, use, and user identity can be true, false, or anything in between.

Objects lie on behalf of designers, manufacturers, sellers, or users, all of whom lie to gain advantages. Lies are means to ends. Lies are instrumental in making somebody believe something untrue that the liar prefers to the truth. Here we shall define counterfactual design as design that, by its appearance, misleads the spectator to form an opinion about the substance that the sender prefers to the truth.

Nobel Laureate Herbert Simon told us that 'everybody is a designer who devises courses of action aimed at leading from present situations to preferred situations' [5]. Counterfactual design represents a shortcut between present and preferred situations. The motivation behind counterfactual design can be dislike of the present situation, longing for a preferred situation, or both. For example, the hooded bank robber wants to hide his true identity. The Elvis impersonator wants to become 'the King,' and the girl who bleaches her hair hates the existing mouse brown shade as much as she longs for the capillary blondness.

Man is not alone in taking material truth easily. Animals also pretend, exaggerate, underplay, and suppress. With animals, as with humans, the absence of truth can be permanent or conditioned by the specific situation. The flying stick and several other insects practice mimicry pretending permanently to be something that they are not, while chameleons, and many other species save the disguise for special occasions such as foraging, procreation, and defence.

Counterfactual design covers several possibilities from the most innocent beautification of reality to criminal deception. The dress that makes the buxom girl appear slimmer populates the same truth-bending continuum as the counterfeiter's homemade hundred dollar bills. Here we shall classify counterfactual design according to four objectives: *beautification*, *amusement*, *ersatz*, and *deception*. Beautification and amusement relate closely to the first two positions on the truth-bending continuum: truth edited and truth on standby respectively. Ersatz relates, depending on the circumstances, to truth on standby or truth suspended. Finally, deception always relates to truth suspended.

Beautification deals with improvement, amusement deals with otherness, ersatz with likeness, and deception with cheating. These four objectives are not mutually exclusive. A toupee, a small hairpiece to cover baldness,

serves both as beautification and ersatz. Table 1 visualizes the relations between the degree of truth bending, the objective of truth bending, and the keywords describing the design effort.

Table 1: Classes of counterfactual design

Truth bending	Objective	Keyword
Truth edited	Beautification	Improvement
Truth standby	Amusement	Otherness
	Ersatz	Likeness
Truth suspended		
	Deception	Cheating

6. Modes of counterfactual design

The classification of counterfactual design serves to illuminate the subject matter by identifying differences and similarities. The truth bending classes, truth edited, truth on standby, and truth suspended describe degrees of seduction, *how much* the message told by counterfactual design differs from the truth, while the objectives of beautification, amusement, ersatz, and deception describe the objectives behind counterfactual design. Modes of seduction, a third classification of counterfactual design, codify not how much, but *how* counterfactually designed objects deviate from the truth: in what way the surface deviates from the substance. The truth bending classes are quantitative categories, while the modes of seduction describe qualitative differences between surface and substance.

In his essay *Simulation and Dissimulation*, the 16th century English philosopher Francis Bacon devised three ways a person purposely could hide and veil his self: by secrecy, dissimulation, and simulation [6]. Secrecy meant keeping a low profile, while dissimulation hid something unwanted, and simulation presented something untrue. Counterfactual design, however, is not limited to hiding and veiling. Beautification, amusement, ersatz, and deception also include more active elements such as showing off and bluffing. Counterfactual design calls for different categories. We shall call our modes *overstatement*, *fabrication*, *understatement*, and *hiding*. Fabrication relates to Bacon's simulation. Hiding relates to Bacon's dissimulation and secrecy. Overstatement and understatement fall outside Bacon's classes. Table 2 visualizes the relations between Bacon's hiding and veiling categories and the modes proposed by this paper.

Table 2. Francis Bacon's hiding-and-veiling categories compared with counterfactual design modes

Francis Bacon's categories	Counterfactual design modes
Secrecy	Hiding
Dissimulation	
Simulation	Fabrication
–	Overstatement
–	Understatement

Overstatement is, without exaggeration, the most common type of counterfactual design. High-heeled shoes, 4wds with bull bars, and domestic espresso machines that remind us of the steam engine we never got as children all overstate qualities that are considered attractive. Fabrication covers the production of surfaces that

deliberately misrepresent the substance. Set pieces, props, and theatre dresses are the aristocracy of fabrication. Wigs, artificial limbs, and coffee substitute also belong in this category. Understatement deals with downplay. Clothes that make the wearer appear slimmer fall into this category. Hiding means disappearing from the sight. Military camouflage falls into this category.

Overstatement and understatement can be seen as two sides of the same coin insofar as overstating one quality implies understating the opposite quality. Fabrication can, in some cases, be seen as hiding an unwanted quality, just as a wig hides baldness. Rather than sharply divided and mutually exclusive categories, the counterfactual design modes should be seen as possible qualities of counterfactual design.

The four counterfactual design modes combined with the four objectives inform the matrix with 16 fields, five of which will probably be empty.

Table 3. Counterfactual design objectices and their corresponding modes.

Objective >	Overstatement	Fabrication	Understatement	Hiding
Beautification >	x	x	x	x
Amusement >	?	x	?	?
Ersatz >	?	x	?	x
Deception >	x	x	x	x

7. Overt or covert

Much counterfactual design is overt; the seduction takes place in openness. The openness is even part of the game. Hiding the young girl's high-heeled shoes that make her legs look longer and her walking more intriguing would be counterproductive to the idea of female dressing up. Theatres also do their magic in all openness. The scene complete with backdrop, set pieces, and props pretends to be something, which it is not, but the *aesthetic distance* ensures that the audience knows it is theatre, not reality. *Innocent fraudulence* sounds like an oxymoron, but that is the business of this branch of counterfactual design. Overtly counterfactual design is typically innocent.

Covertly counterfactual design, in contrast, takes place when the designer, manufacturer, seller, or user hides the true character of the designed object by all possible means. A person with an artificial leg likely wants to hide it as best he can. A currency counterfeiter wants to hide the (real) identity of his forged hundred dollar bills. Covertly counterfactual design is innocent in the first case and fraudulent in the second case.

Umberto Eco coined the term *aberrant decoding* [7] to describe the situation where the receiver of a message understands something not intended by the sender. The *sender* of covertly counterfactual design, i.e. the designer, manufacturer, seller, or user, wants the *receiver* to misunderstand. In this case understanding the truth would be aberrant decoding, as far as the sender did not intend it. Misunderstanding the truth would be aberrant decoding as far as reality is concerned.

8. Beautification: Mother of deception

It is a widespread belief that design exclusively deals with giving shape to objects where appearance plays a special role, such as fashion, cars, and beautiful objects for the home. Designers fight this limiting perception of their field of operation claiming that all manmade products are designed. Nevertheless, famous designers typically win their fame by designing *beautiful* objects and environments.

In our increasingly affluent society, the interest for consumption and ownership moves from quantity to quality. We don't eat twice as much food, but better food. It is the same with other consumer goods. Concurrent with movement in preferences from quantity to quality, appearance plays a growing role in our experience of quality. The demand for quality moves from technical values to feelings and communication, to symbolic, and to aesthetic values. Replying to the changes in demand, the market supply becomes sense driven rather than technology driven. Spectacles exemplify this development. In bygone times, spectacles were prosthetics that helped visually impaired citizens to live a better life. Today, the appearance of the glasses is as important as their technical function. The glasses are not only to see with, but also to be seen in. Long ago the optometrist dropped the white coat and the knitted brows, and his shop does not look like the truss maker's outlet anymore. The terms used for glasses illustrate what happened: *spectacles, glasses, eyewear, designer frames*. This development is not specific to glasses, it is seen in many fields. The language reflects the development.

Beautification enters the kingdom of counterfactual design when it covers reality and makes us believe something more or less distant from, and better than, the truth. Counterfactual design includes personal appearance as well as the appearance of our high interest belongings. In these fields, truth is relatively innocently obscured by counterfactual design. As often as not, the truth is edited in openness.

On the personal level, counterfactual design has occurred for long time. Fragrances, make-ups, hair dyes, all kinds of body regulating lingerie, and high-heeled shoes are time honoured female weapons. But men are not left behind; if one can believe advertising, their use of counterfactual body-scents matches, or even surpasses, that of the female sex.

Many kinds of objects can be beautified by counterfactual design. A family car can look sportier than it is. An old wreck of a car can be superficially revamped for sale. History provides ample examples of the truth bending tendency to embellish facts. The proverbial Potemkin Village was counterfactual being facades only to impress the Russian Empress during the visit to the Crimean peninsula in the 18th century. When the southern part of continental Denmark voted itself back from Germany in 1920 the Danish King Christian X symbolically crossed the old border on a white horse. Ever since it has been a widespread belief that the royal horse was *painted* white. That people *believe* the horse was painted supports the cause as much as if the horse *were* painted.

As a category of counterfactual design, beautification is characterised by constituents that primarily exist because of a practical purpose. That purpose may be more or less eclipsed by the beautified appearance.

9. Amusement: Flight of fantasy

Perhaps we all harbour an obscure desire to change identity and be something and somewhere in a time which we are not. Perhaps we want to live a different life, maybe only temporarily. Children's birthday parties, masquerades, dress balls, and acting, where participants transmogrify into new personas, indicate that it is so. Counterfactual design facilitates virtual travels in time and space. It is practised in such fields as theatre, partying and tourist attractions. Amusement is the end.

The theatre's arsenal of backdrops, set pieces, props, and costumes all serve to teleport audiences from their everyday to other times and other places. Objects for everyday use, houses, and entire environments, can also appear in disguise in so-called real life. The bar camouflaged as a bookshelf is a cliché in manor houses cast in films. Theme parks, open-air museums, safari parks, water paradises, and Disney venues offer the grand tour at the price and efforts of a small excursion.

Trompe l'oeil, two dimensional naturalistic pictorial art that is taken for three-dimensional reality is used as decoration in buildings has no practical function. It is pure joy. The deceived spectator enjoys the deception. The same mechanism applies to other kinds of deceptive art, epitomized by Dutch artist M.C. Escher. Amusement as a category of counterfactual design is always quite innocent. The spectator enjoys being fooled. The truth is on standby.

10. Ersatz: Second choice

In this analysis, *ersatz* refers to materials and objects used in the place of those that otherwise would be the natural choice. The natural choice may not be available; it may be too expensive, or too impractical. Ersatz materials and objects replace something against which they are always benchmarked. Margarine replaces butter; butter is the real thing. Margarine is coloured like, and compared with, the real thing.

Necessity is the mother of invention, and ersatz materials and objects are not newcomers. Numerous materials were introduced to replace other materials for the aforementioned reasons. Wallpaper was invented to replace textiles, linoleum was invented to replace leather, Formica was invented to replace wood, and Corian was invented to substitute marble. Veneered furniture was introduced to save expensive wood sorts but also for constructional reasons.

Sometimes ersatz becomes more valuable than the substituted material or object. Nylons – originally invented to replace expensive silk stockings – exemplify this effect. When this happens we tend to forget the origin and stop considering the substitute as ersatz. It becomes something in its own right, the real thing, while the substituted product perhaps fades into oblivion. Leather is sometimes, half jokingly, called *wild plastic*. As a category of counterfactual design ersatz can, dependent on the intention behind it, be bona fide or mala fide, undertaken in good or bad faith. The truth is on standby in the first case and suspended in the second.

Artificial body parts are ersatz that will hardly be preferred to the original parts, but are nevertheless much appreciated both as practical help and as a means to avoid stigmatization. Artificial body parts include hair, lenses, teeth, limbs, pacemakers, and more. Models are abstractions of the real thing. Some physical models try to mimic the original as much as possible, while others just abstract a few relevant characteristics. *Gliedermann* models are articulated imitations of the human skeleton or parts such as hands and feet. Architectural models are typically smaller than life, while an anatomical model of the human eye may be several times larger than life.

Ersatz not only replaces materials and manmade objects, occasionally it also replaces living beings. In the case of *mental commitment robots*, artificial animals mimic some of the real animals' needs for care. Mental commitment robots, such as the Japanese made *Paro*, please those who have an unsatisfied need to give care, e.g. in hospitals and homes for elderly people. The need to care may be as strongly felt as the need for care.

11. Deception: Truth suspended

Counterfactual design bends the truth. Our categories of objectives, beautification, amusement, and to some extent ersatz, include innocent types of counterfactual design, where truth is edited or on standby. The fourth category, deception, includes counterfactual design where truth is suspended. Here we are talking about fraud. Those who are deceived suffer from the deception. Hard-core deception takes place in several fields including warfare, fishing, hunting, gardening, and, of course, in crime including several types of plagiarism, infringement of intellectual property rights.

The martial use of counterfactual design includes, notably, hiding in the shape of camouflage, but also fabrication of threatening presence in order to fool the enemy. The latter method is applied on a smaller scale by gardeners, who keep fruit-eating birds away with scarecrows. Hunters and fishermen use decoys and spoon bait to tempt and attract their prey. Hunters, bird watchers, and animal photographers use camouflage to pass unseen.

Disguise can be more than fun. One thing is dressing up for a masquerade where normal attire is considered abnormal. Another thing is the use of disguise to achieve advantages wrongfully. The latter was the case when the proverbial *Captain from Köpenick*, a town in Prussia, emptied his town's cashbox disguised in a stolen uniform. Bank robbers and aggressive protesters at political summit meetings stereotypically use balaclavas or hoods with eyeholes to remain incognito to staff and surveillance cameras when committing their offence.

The question, if deceptive design is wrongdoing, depends on the vantage point, on moral and on law. To mislead the enemy in war and to befool animals when hunting and fishing are acceptable practices seen from the deceiver's view. Misleading fellow beings to achieve personal gain is considered immoral, and perhaps in conflict with the law. In any case, deception, as defined here, means truth suspended. This is the realm of hard-core seduction.

12. Conclusion

This paper has illustrated that, contrary to the suggestion implicit in the phrase ‘form follows function,’ designed objects are often deceptive and that we their users, sometimes delight in deceiving and being deceived. Designed objects fulfil our emotional, symbolic, and aesthetic needs as well as our utilitarian functional requirements, however only the latter are given any significant attention in the existing literature. This paper has outlined the nature of counterfactual design and suggested a framework for investigating it. In conclusion counterfactual design, design that massages the truth, is an essential design phenomenon that warrants future research, particularly in the area of design practice. If products that please the user tend to have a longer psychological life, there could also be a sustainability aspect in counterfactual design.

13. References

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